
Employee Health and Welfare - A Pathway to Organizational Success

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Abstract: *This article focuses on the health and welfare provisions and its importance and influence on the development of both the employee and the organization.*

In the present global industrial scenario, for any industry to be successful, it is essential to inculcate effective provision of health and welfare measures to employees. Any organization would become dynamic and growth oriented if the employees are motivated to perform better, feel better, and feel comfortable in the place of work. Organization cannot survive beyond a point unless these are continuously alert to the changing environment and continuously prepare their employees to meet the challenges and have an impact on environment as the welfare facility and health conditions are related to environment, providing these facilities will have a lot of impact on their performance and productivity. The term "health" is a positive and dynamic concept and implies more than an absence of illness. Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease (WHO). Medical care and health facilities for industrial workers form an integral part of labour welfare programmes in all the countries of the world. Health measures should be strictly followed to provide conducive working conditions to the employees at place of work. The various welfare measures provided by the employer will have immediate impact on the health, physical and mental efficiency alertness, morale and overall efficiency of the worker and thereby contributing to the higher productivity.

Hence this paper examines the different types of health facilities provided in the organization and awareness of the employees on the same, employee perception on various health provisions, its impact and significance on employee performance and growth of the organization with reference to five star hotels in, Mangalore. The population for the study consists of employees from one of the five star hotels in Mangalore and 50 respondents were taken for the study through systematic random sampling. The study has revealed that health and welfare measures results in high employee performance, contribute towards growth of the business, increase

employee morale and motivation and organization can retain and attract the talented employees.

Key words: *Health welfare and provisions, satisfaction, performance and productivity*

Introduction

The concept of labour health and welfare are flexible and widely differs with respect to time, region, industry, country, social value and customs, degree of industrialization the general socio economic development of the people and political ideologies prevailing during a particular time frame. It is also, molded according to the age group, sex, socio-cultural background, economic status and educational level of workers in various industries. Accordingly, the concept cannot be very precisely defined.

However, the Committee on Labour Welfare (1969) defined the phrase to mean, "Such facilities and amenities as adequate canteens, rest and recreation facilities, sanitary and medical facilities arrangements for travel to and from and for accommodation of workers employed at a distance from their homes, and such other services, amenities and facilities including social security measures as contribute to conditions under which workers are employed."

"Labour or employee welfare is a comprehensive term including various services, benefits and facilities offered to employees by the employer" (Rao, V.S.P. - 2005).

The committee on Labour Welfare in its 1969 report defines Labour Welfare as "social security measures that contribute to improve the condition under which workers are employed in India and health is a general state of physical, mental and emotional well being."

Welfare means faring or doing well. It is a comprehensive term, and refers to the physical, mental and emotional well-being of an individual. Further, the term welfare is a relative concept, relative in time and space. It, therefore, varies from time to time, from region to region and from country to country (Richard Regis, 2008)

Way back in 1931 the Royal Commission on Labour stressed the need of labour welfare primarily because of the harsh treatment meted out to the workers. This need was further emphasized in independent India by the Constitution, (1950) which lays down the following articles in this regard: "Article 42: The State shall make provision for securing just and humane conditions of work....." Discussing the importance of the labour welfare S.T. Edwards (1953) said: "One can buy a man's time, his physical presence

at a particular space, even a few muscular movements, but enthusiasm, initiative, loyalty and devotion to duty cannot be bought. They will have to be created through right employer-employee relations, provision of constructive opportunities for satisfying the major motivating desires of human action. "The basic purpose of employee welfare is to enrich the life of employees and to keep them happy and contented. Welfare measures may be both statutory and non statutory laws require the employer to extend certain benefits to employees in addition to wages or salaries. Organizations provide welfare facilities to their employees to keep their motivation levels high. The employee welfare schemes can be classified into two categories viz. statutory and non-statutory welfare schemes. The statutory schemes are those schemes that are compulsory to provide by an organization as compliance to the laws governing employee health and safety, these include: canteen facilities, drinking water, proper and sufficient lighting, facilities for sitting, changing rooms, first aid appliances, latrines and urinals, washing places, spittoons, rest rooms. Non statutory welfare schemes may include: personal health care, flexi-time, employee assistance programs, harassment policy, employee referral scheme, medi-claim insurance scheme. The various welfare measures provided by the employer will have immediate impact on the health, physical and mental efficiency alertness, morale and overall efficiency of the worker and thereby contributing to the higher productivity.

As a labor-intensive industry, the hospitality industry is always full of quantity employees and employee issues. The human resource management in hospitality industry should focus more on employees themselves. Many hotels and restaurants deliberately flout occupational health and safety rules which are resulting in increased staff turnover, fines and costly pay-outs to employees. (Lye, 2009). Employee's health and welfare is the key to manage the employees well. There is no reason to ignore employee's health and welfare in working place. This outlook motivated the researcher to make an attempt to study the various health and welfare measures in one of the Five Star Hotels in Mangalore.

Review of Literature

A study conducted by Mohan and Panwar (2013) shows that the retail stores at Udaipur are providing not only intramural facilities but also extramural welfare facilities. It is stretching its hands to provide amenities that may improve health and living standards of the employees. The effective and efficient policies and welfare facilities make the employee to perform the job better, which leads to effectiveness of the organization.

Research by Health and Safety executive (2004a) in 19 case study organizations such as Astrazeneca, SevernTrent Water and Transco etc, established that the tangible benefits from better health and safety and management include higher productivity, lower absence, avoiding the cost of accidents and litigation, meeting client demands and improved staff morale and employee relation.

Logasakthi and Rajagopal (2013) in their study revealed that employees enjoy not only the satisfaction of their jobs but also various facilities given by the firms. The labourers extend their maximum support for the improvement of the company. The personal department takes care of the total human resources in the company. The Management provides all the health safety and welfares to the employees that will help to produce better performance in the work and working environment.

Report of National Commission on Labour (2002), Government of India, made recommendations in the area of labour welfare measures which include social security, extending the application of the Provident Fund, Gratuity and Unemployment Insurance etc.

Ronald C Politnikoff (2009) conducted a research on relationship between workplace environment and physical activity and the results show positive relationship.

V. V. Giri National Labour Institute(1999-2000), a fully funded autonomous body of the Ministry of Labour has conducted action-oriented research and provides training to grass root level workers in the Trade Union Movement, both in the urban and rural areas, and also to officers dealing with industrial relations, personal management, labour welfare, etc.

Webb (1989) also studied a workstation change and found out an increase of 1000% in productivity within less than three months. These changes are mechanical and physical, for example a change of postures to reduce physical strain of work and use of appropriate machinery for some tasks. Improving the fit between humans and tools inherently means a more effective match, good design permits more output with less human effort (MacLeod, 1995). Improving the quality of the workplace environment promotes productivity and companies need to undertake occupational Health and Safety practices that achieve this.

Gunnar Aronsson (2010) found out in his study physical environment and employee health, a remarkable improvement of employee performance.

In the view of K.K. Chaudhuri, in his “Human Resources: A Relook to the Workplace”, states that HR policies are being made flexible. From leaves to compensations, perks to office facilities, many companies are willing to customize policies to suit different employee segments.

Business and Market (2009) analyzed that the “welfare” is a broad concept referring to a state of living of an individual or group, in a desirable relationship with the total environment - ecological, economic and social.

Gerald (2010) conducted a study on the organizational benefits of investing in work place health and the results show positive behavior from employees.

Conventions and Recommendations of ILO (1949) sets forth a fundamental principle at its 26th conference held in Philadelphia recommended some of the measures in the area of welfare measures which include adequate protection for life and health of workers in all occupations, provision for child welfare and maternity protection, provision of adequate nutrition, housing and facilities for recreation and culture, the assurance of equality of educational and vocational opportunity etc.

P.L. Rao, in his “Labour Legislation in the Making”, opines that professional bodies like National Institute of Personnel Management should constitute a standing Committee to monitor the proceedings in the Parliament regarding the labour welfare measures.

Methodology

The research design used for the study was descriptive in nature. The universe of this study consisted of all the employees in one of the five star hotels in Mangalore and 50 respondents were selected for the study through systematic random sampling technique. The questionnaire was distributed to all the respondents by the researcher.

Results and Discussions

Profile of the respondents

Total number of respondents of the study is 50. Among them majority of the respondents belonged to the age group of 21-30 years and 80% of the respondents are male employees. 20 respondents are graduates and majority 44% of the respondents are having below 5 years of work experience.

Table 1: Awareness on health and welfare measures.

Sl. No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes	50	100
2	No	0	0
Total		50	100

The above table shows that 50 (100%) respondents have said they are aware of health and welfare measures provided by the organization.

The above table interprets that all the respondents are aware about the health and welfare measures provided in their organization.

Figure 1: Health and welfare measures and employee performance.

The above figure shows that 40(80%) respondents have strongly agreed that high employee performance results from better health and welfare measures offered by the organisation, whereas 10 (20%) respondents have agreed and none of them have disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Table: 2 Health and welfare measures contribute towards the growth of the business.

Sl. No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	38	76
2	Agree	12	24
3	Disagree	0	0
4	Strongly disagree	0	0
	Total	50	100

The above table discloses that, 38 (76%) respondents strongly agreed that health and welfare measures contribute towards the growth of the business, whereas 12 (24%) respondents agreed and none of them disagreed and strongly disagreed with the above statement.

The above analysis indicates that majority (38 (76%) of the respondents agreed that health and welfare measures contribute towards the growth of the business.

Figure 2: Health and welfare measures increase employee's motivation and morale.

The above figure demonstrates that, 35 (70%) respondents strongly agreed that health and welfare measures increase employee's motivation and morale in the organization, 12 (24%) respondents agreed, 3 (6%) respondents disagreed and none of them strongly disagreed with the above statement.

The above data clearly indicates that majority (35 (70%) of the respondents agreed that health and welfare measures increase employee's motivation and morale in the organisation.

Table 3: Health and welfare measures help organisation to retain the talented employees.

Sl. No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	37	74
2	Agree	13	26
3	Disagree	0	0
4	Strongly disagree	0	0
Total		50	100

The above table shows that, 37 (74%) of respondents strongly agreed with the opinion that health and welfare measures help to retain talented employees, 13 (26%) respondents agreed none of them disagreed and strongly disagreed with the above opinion.

From the above data the researcher found that the majority (37 (74%) of the respondents strongly agreed that through health and welfare measures organisation can retain the talented employees.

Table 4: Health and welfare measures reduce labour turn over.

Sl. No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	23	46
2	Agree	27	54
3	Disagree	0	0
4	Strongly disagree	0	0
Total		50	100

The above table shows that, 23 (46%) respondents strongly agreed that health and welfare measures reduce labour turnover, 27 (54%) respondents agreed, none of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed with this.

The above data clearly indicates that majority (27 (54%) of the respondents agreed that health and welfare measures reduce labour turn over in the organisation.

Figure 3: Health and welfare measures help to remove industrial fatigue.

The above figure depicts that, 27 (54%) respondents strongly agreed that welfare measures help to remove industrial fatigue, 20 (40%) respondents agreed, 3 (6%) respondents disagreed and none of them have strongly agreed with the statement.

The above data clearly indicates that majority (27 (54%) of the respondents agreed that welfare measures help to remove industrial fatigue.

Table 5: Health and welfare measures help to increase better employee-management relationship.

Sl. No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	28	56
2	Agree	22	44
3	Disagree	0	0
4	Strongly disagree	0	0
	Total	50	100

The above table shows, 23 (56%) respondents strongly agreed that health and welfare measures increase better employee-management relationship in the organization, 22 (44%) respondents agreed, none of them disagreed and strongly disagreed with this.

The above data clearly indicates that majority (23 (56%) of the respondents agreed that the welfare measures increase better employee-management relationship in the organisation.

Table 6: Health and welfare measures help to attract suitable and competent employees.

Sl. No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	30	60
2	Agree	20	40
3	Disagree	0	0
4	Strongly disagree	0	0
Total		50	100

The above table shows, 30 (60%) respondents strongly agreed that a health and welfare measure helps to attract suitable and competent employees, 20(40%) respondents agreed, none of them disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement.

The above data clearly indicates that majority (30 (60%) of the respondents agreed that health and welfare measures help to attract suitable and competent employees.

Figure 4: Canteen facility.

The above diagram shows that, 21 (42%) respondents are highly satisfied with canteen facilities provided in the organization, 26 (52%) respondents are satisfied; 3 (6%) respondents are dissatisfied and none of them highly dissatisfied.

The above data clearly indicates that majority (26 (52%)) of the respondents are satisfied with canteen facility provided in the organisation.

Table 7: Transport facility.

Sl. No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Highly Satisfied	34	68
2	Satisfied	16	32
3	Dissatisfied	0	0
4	Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
	Total	50	100

The above table shows that, 34 (68%) respondents are highly satisfied with transport facilities provided by the organization, 16 (32%) respondents are satisfied; none of them are dissatisfied and highly dissatisfied.

The above data clearly indicates that majority (34 (68%)) of the respondents are highly satisfied with transport facilities provided in the organisation.

Table 8: Drinking water facility.

Sl. No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Highly Satisfied	28	56
2	Satisfied	19	38
3	Dissatisfied	3	6
4	Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
	Total	50	100

The above table shows that 28 (56%) respondents are highly satisfied with drinking water provided in the organization, 19 (38%) respondents are satisfied; 3 (6%) respondents are dissatisfied and none the respondents are highly dissatisfied.

The above data clearly indicates that majority (28 (56%) of the respondents are highly satisfied with drinking facility provided in the organisation.

Table 9: Housing facility.

Sl. No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Highly Satisfied	24	48
2	Satisfied	22	44
3	Dissatisfied	4	8
4	Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
	Total	50	100

The above table shows that 24 (48%) respondents are highly satisfied with housing facility provided by the organization, 22 (44%) respondents are satisfied, 4 (8%) respondents are dissatisfied and none of them were highly dissatisfied.

The above data clearly indicate that majority (24 (48%) of the respondents are highly satisfied with housing facility provided by the organisation.

Figure 5: Recreation facility

The above figure shows that, 14 (28%) respondents are highly satisfied with recreation facility provided by the organization, 27(54%) respondents are satisfied; 7 (14%) respondents are dissatisfied and 2 (4%) respondents are highly dissatisfied.

The above data clearly indicate that majority (27 (54%) of the respondents are satisfied with recreation facility provided by the organisation.

Figure 6: social and cultural activities being practiced at the organisation help to improve interpersonal relation with superiors, colleagues and subordinates.

The above table and diagram show that, 29 (58%) respondents have strongly agreed that social and cultural activities help to improve interpersonal relation with superiors, colleagues and subordinates in the organization, 21 (42%) respondents agreed none of respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement.

The above data clearly indicate that majority (29 (58%) of the respondents agreed that social and cultural activities help to improve interpersonal relation with superiors, colleagues and subordinates in the organisation.

Table 10: Need for further improvement in welfare measures in the organization.

Sl. No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes	50	100
2	No	0	0
	Total	50	100

The above table shows that, 50 (100%) respondents have said that there is a need for further improvement in health and welfare measures in the organisation.

From the above data the researcher found that all (50 (100%) the respondents felt the need for further improvement in welfare measures in the organization.

Suggestions

Based on the findings and experience gathered from the present study the following suggestions can be made:

1. The organization should communicate health and welfare facilities available in the organization to all the employees at the time of induction itself.
2. By providing outstanding health and welfare provisions organization can retain and attract talented employees.
3. The organisation should make some changes and improvement in the existing recreation facility by providing room for Table tennis, Chess, Carom etc.
4. Separate recreation room should be provided for male and female employees.
5. All the employees should go through the medical check-up at least once in a year.
6. First aid facility should always be available in the organization at the time of accidents.
7. The organization should give more importance to loan and advance facility to the employees in order to meet their emergency.
8. Accommodation facility for bachelors should be provided with full-fledged kitchen facility.
9. Transport facility, should be provided to all those who are working in different shifts.
10. There is a need to improve the drinking water facility. The drinking water should not be either too cold or too hot to drink.
11. Organization should re-examine and revise its health and welfare schemes in regular intervals in order to make it fit for the present circumstances.

Conclusion

The health and welfare is a very important aspect in an industry. No organisation can ever think of not providing welfare facilities or do away with existing welfare facilities. The various laws emphasise on the welfare of the employees, that is though giving importance to welfare of the employee and health aspect of the employees. Welfare services are something beyond the reciprocal compensation that is paid for the services rendered by labour. The quality of a company's welfare facilities determine and enhance its image as a caring employer. Employee health and welfare facilities have proven to be an excellent tool for the employee retention and improving of organization's bottom line.

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